

Graphical Abstract

A novel mechanistic modelling approach for microbial selection dynamics: towards improved design and control of raceway reactors for purple bacteria

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Highlights

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- New mechanistic model for purple phototrophic bacteria (PPB) is developed.
- A novel empirical constant is introduced for parallel metabolic growth.
- Most impactful parameters are identified by sensitivity analysis.
- Kinetic parameters are calibrated through dedicated experiments.
- Likely-to-occur perturbations are simulated to assess process performance.

A novel mechanistic modelling approach for microbial selection dynamics: towards improved design and control of raceway reactors for purple bacteria

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Abstract

Purple phototrophic bacteria (PPB) form an appealing guild for resource recovery from wastewater, relying on their light-driven metabolism. Raceway reactors offer a more affordable full-scale solution on wastewater and enable useful additional aerobic processes. Current mathematical models of PPB systems provide useful mechanistic insights, but not represent the various metabolic versatility of PPB and thus require further advancement to simulate the process for technology development and control. This study proposes

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a new modelling approach for PPB that integrates the photoheterotrophic, and both anaerobic and aerobic chemoheterotrophic metabolic pathways through an empirical parallel metabolic growth constant. This enables the modelling of microbial selection dynamics in competition with aerobic and anaerobic microbial community under different operational scenarios. A sensitivity analysis is carried out to identify the most influential parameters within the model and calibrate them based on experimental data. Process perturbation scenarios are simulated, which shows a good performance of the model.

Keywords: bio-process modelling, process design, physico-chemical process, resource recovery, purple non-sulphur bacteria.

1. Introduction

Purple phototrophic bacteria (PPB) offer great potential to recover resources from wastewater like organics and the nutrients nitrogen and phosphorus. The phototrophically produced biomass have circular economy applications as microbial fertilizer, biostimulant, animal feed ingredient, and bioplastics feedstock (Alloul et al., 2023; Capson-Tojo et al., 2020). PPB are metabolically diverse and versatile microorganisms with the ability to adapt and grow on the sources of energy (photo- and chemotrophy), electrons (organo- and lithotrophy) and carbon (auto- and heterotrophy) (Imhoff, 2006). As phototrophs, they have the unique ability to grow on infrared light, are anoxygenic and proliferate swiftly in anaerobic mixed-culture systems fed with volatile fatty acids (VFAs). For wastewater treatment and resource recovery, this photoorganoheterotrophic mode is mostly studied (Capson-Tojo

14 et al., 2020).

15 In research labs, membrane (photo)bioreactors, tubular photobioreac-
16 tors, flat-plate photobioreactors, as well as stirred-tank photobioreactors
17 have been mainly used to achieve high PPB selectivity (Alloul et al., 2021a;
18 Capson-Tojo et al., 2020; Cerruti et al., 2020; Hülsen et al., 2022). Success-
19 ful selection of PPB has been mainly obtained in closed configurations to
20 maintain an anaerobic reactor environment. However, the high capital ex-
21 penditure of these systems may prevent implementation at full scale (Acién
22 et al., 2012; Alloul et al., 2021a). Open raceway reactors have reduced total
23 investment and operational cost 5 to 10-fold, relative to closed anaerobic
24 photobioreactors (Alloul et al., 2021a). However, open raceway ponds are
25 exposed to passive oxygenation ($217\text{--}226\text{mgO}_2\text{L}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$ through the combi-
26 nation of the paddle wheel rotation used to circulate the wastewater and their
27 high atmospheric surface-to-volume ratio used to maximize light accessibility
28 ($5\text{ m}^2\text{ m}^3$). Such an uncontrolled supply of dissolved oxygen enables aerobic
29 conversions, bringing PPB also in competition with aerobic bacteria (AEB)
30 for organics. Achieving high PPB selectivity is, therefore, more challeng-
31 ing than in closed anaerobic systems. Nonetheless, changing the operational
32 conditions in terms of oxygen supply, light availability, sludge retention time
33 (SRT), and chemical oxygen demand (COD) loading was successful to boost
34 the PPB abundance from 14 % to 78 % in a 100-L raceway reactor operated
35 on synthetic wastewater (Alloul et al., 2021a).

36 Mechanistic simulation models are needed to improve the design and op-
37 eration of PPB processes, boost piloting activities, scale up implementa-
38 tions, and control the processes. On a more fundamental basis, genome-scale

39 metabolic models have been developed to describe biohydrogen production in
40 pure-culture systems (Golomysova et al., 2010; Imam et al., 2011); however,
41 they cannot be directly used for environmental biotechnology applications.
42 Puyol et al. (2017) have translated the activated sludge model formalism to
43 predict nutrient conversions driven by PPB Henze et al. (2015). The Photo-
44 anaerobic model (PAnM) is limited to photo-anaerobic conditions and does
45 not take microbial competition with non-PPB guilds like aerobic and fer-
46 mentative chemoorganoheterotrophs and photolithoautotrophs into account.
47 The extended version of PAnM (ePAnM) has been proposed by (Capson-
48 Tojo et al., 2023), which integrates eight different types of microorganisms,
49 i.e. PPB, AEB, acidogenic and acetogenic fermenters, aerobic predators,
50 heterotrophic and autotrophic sulphate reducing bacteria, and microalgae
51 and takes diverse metabolic capabilities of PPB into account. Compared
52 to PAnM, PPB photoheterotrophic, aerobic and anaerobic uptake rates and
53 yields have been used to simulate PPB growth in batch and semicontin-
54 uous processes in the ePAnM. As far as observed, the difference in maxi-
55 mum growth rate in relation to PPBs metabolic versatility under various
56 environmental conditions was not explicitly addressed Puyol et al. (2017);
57 Capson-Tojo et al. (2023). Although ePAnM is cable of adapting to varying
58 environmental conditions, authors propose it to be recalibrated for opera-
59 tion of open pond raceway reactors considering different gas-liquid transfers
60 and oxygen circulation from either atmosphere or paddle wheel. With the
61 technological development of PPB raceway systems, a more comprehensive
62 model is necessary to simulate wastewater treatment along with microbial
63 selection to assess operational and control scenarios for raceway reactors and

64 also taking parallel metabolic growth into account. Such model will allow to
65 better engineer, implement, and control raceway reactors by predicting pro-
66 cess conditions, variations, and perturbations that affect the PPB abundance
67 and the treatment performance.

68 In this study, a new mechanistic purple bacterial model (PBM) is con-
69 structed that considers the most relevant metabolic growth modes that PPB
70 and competing microbes including aerobic and anaerobic heterotrophic bac-
71 teria within a raceway reactor for the purpose of process simulation. This
72 model also introduces an empirical constant for accounting parallel metabolic
73 growth pathways, that introduces a starting point to better account for
74 metabolic diversity within a trophic group in these types of models. Af-
75 ter model construction, a sensitivity analysis is conducted to identify the
76 most influential parameters and to assess the impact of parameter variations
77 on the model outputs. Calibration of the important factors is carried out
78 through iterative error minimization. Short- and long-term perturbations
79 of incoming soluble organic matters, volatile fatty acid (VFA), suspended
80 solids and light variations are simulated to their effects on PPB abundance
81 and COD removal rate.

82 **2. Materials and methods**

83 *2.1. Model description*

84 This section delves into the model structure and development. The PBM
85 can be transferred to other reactor systems or used as add-on to existing mod-
86 els such as the Activated Sludge Model (ASM), Anaerobic Digestion Model
87 no.1 (ADMn1) or algae-bacteria models e.g., the ALBA model (Batstone

88 et al., 2002; Henze et al., 2015; Casagli et al., 2021). The PBM is also units
89 compatible to the ASM and ADMn1 series of the International Water Asso-
90 ciation (IWA). The PBM consists of 15 state variables with 3 state variables
91 associated with PPB community, and 16 processes including 12 biological
92 and 4 physical processes. The implemented PBM (MATLAB code) is also
93 provided on GitHub at <https://github.com/Ali-Moradvandi/PBM>. A suppli-
94 mentary document consisting of the parameter values to run the simulation
95 can also be found there.

96 *Microbial community:* The microbial biomass is divided in three main cat-
97 egories, namely purple phototrophic bacteria (PPB), aerobic bacteria (AEB)
98 and anaerobic bacteria (ANB), reflecting the main microbial groups thriv-
99 ing in a raceway reactor covered with a selective infrared cover operated
100 on COD-rich wastewater (Alloul et al., 2021a). The PPB-based bacteria is
101 also divided into three subgroups consisted of photoheterotropic grown PPB
102 ($X_{PB,ph}$), aerobic chemoheterotropic grown PPB ($X_{PB,aec}$), and anaerobic
103 chemoheterotropic grown PPB ($X_{PB,anc}$).

104 *Substrates and products:* The incoming COD consists of both particulate
105 and soluble matters. Readily biodegradable COD is divided in a non-volatile
106 fatty acid (S_S) and C2-C6 volatile fatty acid (S_{VFA}) fractions. The growth
107 kinetics and biochemical pathways for both substrates are different (Batstone
108 et al., 2002; Puyol et al., 2017). VFAs and other dissolved organics follow a
109 different uptake pattern, and lead to different selections (Cerruti et al., 2023).
110 Furthermore, subdividing soluble solids based on individual VFA might also
111 be reasonable because VFAs induce different maximal specific growth rates,
112 yet might increase complexity, thereby, making the model impractical for

113 wastewater treatment applications. As nutrients, only inorganic nitrogen
114 (S_{IN}) and phosphorus (S_{IP}) are included, since organic fractions can be
115 hydrolyzed in the preceding fermentation as suggested by Alloul et al. (2021a)
116 for operational functionality of raceway reactors in producing PPB.

117 Since raceway systems are open reactors, the concentration of dissolved
118 oxygen (S_{O_2}) plays an important role, especially since AEB can outcompete
119 PPB. The effect of the paddle wheel on the mass transfer of dissolved oxygen
120 in the liquid phase is also taken into account for modelling. To close carbon,
121 electron and mass balances, the production of carbon dioxide (S_{CO_2}) and
122 hydrogen (S_{H_2}), which can come from non-VFA and VFAs, are included in
123 the model.

124 *Reactor regime:* The mentioned biochemical and physical processes take
125 place in the raceway reactor. The lab-scale and even pilot-scale raceway
126 reactors can be modelled as a single continuous-flow stirred tank (CSTR) due
127 to their reduced dimensions and the high water circulation flow. However,
128 industrial raceway reactors are usually modelled in three zones, i.e., channel,
129 paddle wheel, and sump (Fernández et al., 2016). Sequencing batch with
130 cycles of filling the reactor with influent once a day and turning on the paddle
131 wheel to promote gas transfer during the day, and stopping the paddle wheel
132 to slow down the reactions and settle the biomass during nights prior to
133 purging the excess sludge, is assumed as a modelling of the reactor regime
134 to simulate the real situation in physical models in labs.

135 *Balances and system dynamics equations:* The reactor volume may be
136 varied during filling and extracting phases, especially if they are not done at
137 the same time. Therefore, the mass balances of the soluble materials can be

138 written as follows:

$$\frac{dS_i}{dt} = \frac{S_i^{\text{input}} Q_{\text{inflow}}(t) - S_i(Q_{\text{outflow}}(t) + \frac{dV}{dt})}{V_0} + \sum v_i \rho_i, \quad (1)$$

139 where V , Q_{inflow} , Q_{outflow} , V_0 , v_i , ρ_i denote the reactor volume and the input
140 and output flow rates, the initial volume, the stoichiometric coefficient, and
141 the process rate of the corresponding conversion, respectively, in which the
142 subscript i denotes component name.

143 The mass balances for the particulate materials can be written in a sim-
144 ilar way, while integrating a factor related to hydraulic (HRT) and sludge
145 (SRT) retention times to model the effect of the paddle wheel activation,
146 the effluent extraction, and the water recirculation if needed. This factor is
147 defined as the HRT/SRT ratio ($f_{H/S}$) to consider the fraction of removed
148 particles. The HRT to the SRT provides insights into the performance and
149 stability of the reactor, which should be optimized. The mass balance equa-
150 tion for particulate materials becomes the following, considering transport
151 and conversion terms:

$$\frac{dX_i}{dt} = \frac{X_i^{\text{input}} Q_{\text{inflow}}(t) - X_i(Q_{\text{outflow}}(t) + \frac{dV}{dt} f_{H/S})}{V_0} + \sum v_i \rho_i. \quad (2)$$

152 In addition, the mass balance equation of oxygen is modified to take the
153 effect of oxygen dissolution into account when the paddle wheel is working. A
154 switching function associated with the on/off conditions of the paddle wheel
155 is, therefore, integrated to consider oxygen promotion.

156 *Metabolic versatility of PPB*: Six biological processes were assigned to

157 PPB, namely: two photoheterotrophic growths on soluble organics and VFAs,
158 respectively; two aerobic chemoheterotrophic growths on soluble organics and
159 VFAs, respectively; one anaerobic chemoheterotrophic growth on soluble or-
160 ganics; and biomass decay into biodegradable materials and inerts while re-
161 leasing inorganic nitrogen, phosphorus and carbon. The PPB biomass there-
162 fore comprises grow metabolisms by photoheterotrophy ($X_{PB,ph}$), aerobic
163 chemoheterotrophy ($X_{PB,aec}$), and anaerobic chemoheterotrophy ($X_{PB,anc}$).
164 This subdivision reflects the different types of metabolisms that PPB con-
165 duct in a raceway reactor subjected to varying environmental conditions, e.g.,
166 availability of light, oxygen, fermentable organics, etc. (Alloul et al., 2021a).
167 The model is written to account for the ability of PPB to grow on different
168 substrates (electron donors and carbon sources) or energy sources (light or
169 chemical redox reactions) in parallel. For instance, if light and VFAs are
170 abundant, PPB will mainly grow by photoheterotrophy, and if the dissolved
171 oxygen concentration is high, aerobic chemoheterotrophy by PPB will be fa-
172 vored. The parallel metabolic growth of PPB is implemented in the model
173 by introducing a novel factor and inhibition-type functions with light and
174 oxygen to control photoheterotrophy and chemoheterotrophies, respectively.
175 A parallel metabolic growth constant (M_S) between the three PPB biomass
176 types is included so that biomass is grown phototrophically and chemotroph-
177 ically in parallel during shifting between days and nights. This novel factor is
178 the main difference between the PBM proposed and the PAnM and ePAnM
179 developed by (Puyol et al., 2017; Capson-Tojo et al., 2023) and can be written
180 as follows:

$$f_{ph} = X_{PB,ph} + M_S(X_{PB,aec} + X_{PB,anc}) \quad (3a)$$

$$f_{aec} = X_{PB,aec} + M_S(X_{PB,ph} + X_{PB,anc}) \quad (3b)$$

$$f_{anc} = X_{PB,anc} + M_S(X_{PB,ph} + X_{PB,aec}) \quad (3c)$$

181 where f_{ph} , f_{aec} , and f_{anc} represents state variables with regard to photo-
 182 heterotrophic, aerobic chemoheterotrophic, and anaerobic chemoheterotrophic
 183 growths, respectively used in Table (3).

184 *Microbial competitors:* Microbial processes that compete with PPB meta-
 185 bolisms in the raceway biomass are mainly aerobic chemoheterotrophy by
 186 AEB and anaerobic chemoheterotrophy by ANB. Nitrifiers, methanogens,
 187 denitrifiers and sulfate reducing bacteria were not implemented in the model
 188 since not prevalent in open raceway reactors (Alloul et al., 2021a). It should
 189 be highlighted that the model structure can be adapted with additional pro-
 190 cesses (such as described in ASM and ADM) by users, depending on the local
 191 conditions to be investigated.

192 *Reactor geometry:* Note that The PBM is designed for an open raceway
 193 reactor, yet the model can also be used for other reactor systems such as
 194 tubular or flat plate photobioreactors with some modifications to consider
 195 biofilm formation. Raceway reactors typically have a liquid depth of 20 cm
 196 and a surface-to-volume ratio of $5 \text{ m}^2 \text{ m}^{-3}$ (Norsker et al., 2011).

197 *Gas-liquid transfers:* These systems are open to air and agitated with
 198 a paddle wheel. Gas-liquid mass transfer of four components, is, therefore,
 199 included in the model, namely: oxygen dissolution from the air through

200 paddle wheel rotation; carbon dioxide dissolution from the air or produced
201 through biological processes; hydrogen dissolution from the air or produced
202 through biological processes; and ammonia origination from the incoming
203 wastewater. The mass transfer kinetics for all gases is described through
204 volumetric mass transfer rate and the gas saturation concentration through
205 Henry's law.

206 *Inhibitory factors:* As for the activated sludge model and anaerobic diges-
207 tion model, kinetics expressions are multiplicative and based on Monod type
208 functions to describe limitations of organics, ammonium, phosphate, light,
209 and oxygen. In comparison with the PAnM (Puyol et al., 2017) and ePAnM
210 (Capson-Tojo et al., 2023), since the PBB community is not considered as a
211 single cell in the PBM, light inhibitory factor is differentiated between photo-
212 heterotrophy and chemoheterotrophy. Moreover, different oxygen inhibitions
213 are taken into account for PBB photoheterotrophy and chemoheterotrophy
214 as well as aerobic and anaerobic microbial communities. Competitive inhibi-
215 tion function between VFAs and other soluble organics is also included into
216 the PBM as PBB growth competition has been reported by (Cerruti et al.,
217 2020).

218 *Light irradiance and attenuation:* Light is a crucial input factor to sup-
219 port the phototrophic growth of PPB. The average light intensity in the
220 bioreactor is determined based on Lambert-Beer's Law, which is formulated
221 in the form of an inhibition function to differentiate light illumination be-
222 tween day and night. Light attenuation (Solimeno et al., 2017) is also taken
223 into account in function of the biomass concentration to formulate a close-
224 to-real-world condition for light intensity.

225 *2.2. Model analysis*

226 In this section, the methodology employed to analyze the PBM is de-
227 scribed. Sensitivity analysis was carried out to first identify the influential
228 parameters of the model, then calibrate these impactful model parameters
229 using data from controlled experiments. The robustness of the model is as-
230 sessed by simulating the model under different operational scenarios.

231 *Sensitivity analysis:* After model construction, a local sensitivity analysis
232 was conducted to assess the impact of each parameter on the PBM. The PBM
233 contains various parameters, ranging from physical to kinetic parameters,
234 in which physical parameters and yields have been broadly researched and
235 validated. Total kinetic parameters including maximal specific growth rates
236 (μ_m), substrate affinities (K_S), inhibition constants (K_I), and specific decay
237 rate (b_m) associated with microbial community are covered in the sensitivity
238 analysis, which a part of them is directly linked to PPB.

239 The default value of each parameter is varied one by one, ten times
240 higher and lower (Manhaeghe et al., 2020). As baseline, kinetic parame-
241 ters are obtained from previous research from the authors, literature, the
242 activated sludge model and anaerobic digestion model. Newly-defined pa-
243 rameters, such as PPB oxygen affinities, have been chosen based on the
244 experiments, trial and error, as well as the expert knowledge. All parameter
245 variations are considered to be uniformly distributed. The duration time of
246 each simulation is set to 50 days to ensure reaching the steady-state condi-
247 tion. The relative abundance of PPB, COD removal rate ($\text{mg COD L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$),
248 biomass productivity ($\text{mg COD L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$) and biomass yield ($\text{mg COD}_{\text{biomass}}$
249 $\text{mg}^{-1} \text{COD}_{\text{removed}}$) are selected as outputs because of their feasibility to

250 measure for the experiments. The mean of the model output for the last
251 five days (when the process reaches steady-state) for each iteration is calcu-
252 lated and divided by the output of the baseline (default values) to obtain
253 the relative error. The wastewater composition for the sensitivity analysis is
254 considered based on the synthetic medium proposed by Alloul et al. (2021a).

255 *Calibration and validation:* Based on the sensitivity analysis, five impact-
256 ful PPB-related parameters are selected for calibration, which have not been
257 previously calibrated in the literature, namely the oxygen half-saturation
258 constant for chemotrophic growth of PPB ($K_{S,O2,PPB}$), oxygen inhibitory con-
259 stant for phototrophic growth of PPB ($K_{I,O2,PPB}$), light half-saturation con-
260 stant of PPB ($K_{S,E}$), light inhibitory constant for chemotrophic growth of
261 PPB ($K_{I,E}$) and the parallel metabolic growth constant (M_S).

262 For calibration, experimental data from a previous study was used, which
263 conducted a controlled experiment in a 100-L pilot scale raceway reac-
264 tor with a mixed PPB culture dominated by *Rhodobacter capsulatus* and
265 a *Rhodospseudomonas* (Alloul et al., 2021a). The reactor has been operated
266 for 40 days on synthetic wastewater at a temperature of 28 °C and illumi-
267 nated artificially with halogen lamps (50 W m⁻²). The raceway had a depth
268 of 10–20 cm and a surface-to-volume ratio of 5–10 m² m⁻³. Three opera-
269 tional strategies were tested as: (i) 24 h stirring at a surface-to-volume ratio
270 of 5 m² m⁻³ with a 12 h light and 12 h dark regime (scenario 1), (ii) 12 h stir-
271 ring during the light period at a surface-to-volume ratio of 5 m² m⁻³ with a
272 12 h light and 12 h dark regime (scenario 2), (iii) 24 h stirring at a surface-to-
273 volume ratio of 10 m² m⁻³ with a 12 h light and 12 h dark regime (scenario
274 3)

275 A relevant range for each of the five parameters was selected based on
276 expert knowledge and sensitivity analysis. All possible combinations of the
277 five parameters were then computed for the three mentioned operational
278 strategies. The mean of the last five simulated days along with the relative
279 error was, then, calculated for each iteration of every individual outputs, i.e.
280 relative abundance of PPB, COD removal rate, biomass productivity and
281 biomass yield. The parameter combination with the lowest relative error for
282 each model output and a similar trend in output over the three strategies
283 were selected.

284 *Perturbed scenario assessment:* The calibrated model can be used to im-
285 prove the design and operation of PPB-based reactors. In pilot and full-scale
286 systems, for example, process and environmental perturbation can influence
287 the stability of the PPB community and wastewater treatment performance.
288 Four short-term perturbations, likely to occur in a full-scale PPB system,
289 are simulated to assess the effect of the perturbations on the model, namely
290 as: (i) incoming VFA concentration (250, 500, and 3000 mgCODL⁻¹d⁻¹),
291 (ii) incoming soluble organic matters (0, 100, and 3000 mgCODL⁻¹d⁻¹), (iii)
292 incoming suspended solids (0, 250, 1000 mgCODL⁻¹d⁻¹), and (iv) the light
293 intensity (14, 54, 108 W m⁻²). The simulation is run for 25 days at a 12 h
294 light and 12 h dark condition and stirring regime of 12 h on and 12 h off to
295 reach steady-state and the perturbations are, then, implemented.

296 **3. Results and discussion**

297 In this section, results and associated discussions of the methods employed
298 to build and analyze the model is discussed.

299 *Sensitivity analysis:* The sensitivity analysis provides the influential pa-
300 rameters for further calibration. The impacts of the most sensitive param-
301 eters are listed in Table 4 and ranked based on PPB abundance impact.
302 Maximal specific growth rates (μ_m), specific decay rates (b_m) and kinetic
303 parameters related to oxygen as well as light constants have the greatest im-
304 pact on the PPB abundance. Substrate half-saturation constants (K_S) such
305 as the soluble organic for phototrophic and chemotrophic growth of PPB
306 and VFA for chemotrophic and aerobic heterotrophic growth of PPB did not
307 show any or only a very low impact (close to zero). Similar results have
308 been also reported by Biase et al. (2021), for a high-rate moving bed biofilm
309 reactor model, which showed that the aerobic decay rate and maximal spe-
310 cific growth rate of AEB had a 5–12 times stronger impact on the model
311 compared to substrate half-saturation constants.

312 The effect of parameter variation on the model output is only impactful in
313 a specific range, typically between 0.50–5.45 times the baseline values based
314 on the sensitivity analysis. Furthermore, the sensitivity analysis shows that
315 the relative PPB abundance is more sensitive to parameter variations com-
316 pared to the other model outputs. This is because of splitting PBB commu-
317 nity and differentiating among light and oxygen inhibitions to build a model
318 more accurate in terms of predicting PPB abundance. This also reflects the
319 challenge to construct a model, which predicts relative PPB abundances.

320 Overall, the maximal specific growth rate of AEB on soluble organics
321 ($\mu_{m,SS,AEB}$) has the most impact on the model output. AEB are in direct
322 competition with PPB for COD, nutrients, and oxygen. Higher maximal
323 specific growth rates of AEB directly influences the microbial community

324 distribution and the COD removal rates. This is also the reason why passive
325 oxygen entry into a raceway reactor should be minimized to suppress the
326 growth of competing AEB. For example, preventing oxygen entry during the
327 night by paddle wheel control is a key strategy to boost the PPB abundance
328 from 14 to 56 % (Alloul et al., 2021a). The importance of oxygen for PPB
329 communities is also reconfirmed by Alloul et al. (2021b). The second most im-
330 pactful parameter is the maximal specific aerobic chemoheterotrophic growth
331 rate of PPB on VFA ($\mu_{m,VFA, PB, aec}$). This parameter is essential to allow
332 competition of PPB with AEB under dark aerobic conditions. The maximal
333 specific aerobic chemoheterotrophic growth rate of PPB on soluble organics
334 ($\mu_{m, SS, PB, aec}$) is also within the most impactful parameters, however, this
335 parameter is less sensitive compared to the maximal specific aerobic chemo-
336 heterotrophic growth rate of PPB on VFA ($\mu_{m,VFA, PB, aec}$).

337 Next to maximal specific growth rates, the sensitivity analysis also shows
338 that all three parameters related to oxygen have a strong impact on the
339 model. These are the oxygen half-saturation constants for chemoheterotrophic
340 growth of PPB ($K_{S,O_2, PB}$), and AEB ($K_{S,O_2, AEB}$), and oxygen inhibitory
341 constant for phototrophic growth of PPB ($K_{I,O_2, PB}$). This is a key differ-
342 ence with the previous versions of the models proposed for purple bacteria
343 (Puyol et al., 2017; Capson-Tojo et al., 2023). As mentioned before, PPB pi-
344 lot implementation is moving towards raceway systems (Alloul et al., 2023).
345 These reactors typically have low dissolved oxygen concentrations around
346 $0.0\text{--}0.2\text{ mgO}_2\text{L}^{-1}$ because the paddle wheel only passively transfers oxygen
347 into the systems (maximal oxygen transfer rate $217\text{--}226\text{ mgO}_2\text{L}^{-1}\text{ d}^{-1}$). At
348 these low dissolved oxygen concentrations, oxygen half-saturation constants

349 play a major role in the competition between chemoheterotrophically grown
350 PPB and AEB. This is the reason why the oxygen half-saturation constant
351 for both aerobically grown PPB and AEB have such a strong impact on the
352 microbial community distribution.

353 From literature, it is also known that PPB cannot compete at high dis-
354 solved oxygen concentrations in illuminated reactors (Capson-Tojo et al.,
355 2021). This can be due to direct oxygen inhibition and loss of pigments
356 (indirect inhibition). This phenomenon has been observed for *Rhodospiril-*
357 *lum rubrum* at dissolved oxygen concentration above $0.40 \text{ mgO}_2\text{L}^{-1}$. Thus
358 far, there is no research available on direct oxygen inhibition of phototrophic
359 grown PPB. This sensitivity analysis, however, shows that the oxygen in-
360 hibitory constant for phototrophic growth of PPB ($K_{I,O_2,PPB}$) is also an im-
361 pactful parameter in the model, which particularly impacts the PPB abun-
362 dance. When it is higher, phototrophically grown PPB will be less sensitive
363 to oxygen, and thus higher relative abundances can be achieved.

364 An open raceway pond is an illuminated system. Two light-related pa-
365 rameters are, therefore, included in the model, namely the light half-saturation
366 constant of PPB ($K_{S,E}$) and light inhibitory constant for chemotrophic growth
367 of PPB ($K_{I,E}$), which are in the list of the most impactful kinetic param-
368 eters. Katsuda et al. (2000) have reported 0.12 W m^{-2} for a pure culture
369 of *Rb. capsulatus* illuminated with tungsten lamps. Moreover, Capson-Tojo
370 et al. (2022) have estimated it as 4.58 W m^{-2} through anaerobic microplates
371 tests for mixed PPB cultures. Light inhibitory constant for chemotrophic
372 growth of PPB ($K_{I,E}$) regulates the (an)aerobic chemotrophic growth of
373 PPB. At high light intensities, it is expected that the PPB community shifts

374 its metabolic labor towards phototrophy, thereby, hampering chemotrophic
375 growth. Thus far, the light inhibitory constant for PPB's chemotrophic
376 growth has not been reported in literature, because PPB research is domi-
377 nated by anaerobic systems, which do not account for aerobic chemoheterotro-
378 phy. The sensitivity analysis, however, shows that it is a crucial parameter
379 as it severely impacts the model's output.

380 A parallel metabolic growth constant (M_S) between the three PPB biomass
381 types is an innovative part of the PBM introduced in this paper, there-
382 fore that biomass grown photoheterotrophically is also able to use chemo-
383 heterotrophic conversion and vice versa. PPB are known to divide their
384 metabolic growth pathways over photo- and chemotrophy. An M_S of zero
385 implies that PPB biomass grown photoheterotrophically cannot switch to
386 chemoheterotrophy and is, therefore, completely independent of chemoheterotro-
387 phy.

388 Overall, the sensitivity analysis uncovered the impactful parameters of the
389 PBM. Specifically the parameters $K_{S,O_2,PB}$, $K_{I,O_2,PB}$, $K_{S,E}$, $K_{I,E}$ and M_S are
390 thus far unreported or only limited-studied, yet have a strong impact on the
391 model. Therefore, the calibration of these five parameters and comparison
392 of the simulated output with experimental data of a raceway reactor are
393 presented in the following.

394 *Calibration and validation:* According to the sensitivity analysis, five im-
395 pactful PPB-related parameters were identified that are not described in
396 literature and not yet calibrated for a raceway reactor, namely the oxy-
397 gen half-saturation constant for aerobic chemoheterotrophic growth of PPB
398 ($K_{S,O_2,PB}$), oxygen inhibitory constant for phototrophic growth of PPB ($K_{I,O_2,PB}$),

399 light half-saturation constant of PPB ($K_{S,E}$), light inhibitory constant for
400 chemotrophic growth of PPB ($K_{I,E}$) and the parallel metabolic growth fac-
401 tor (M_S) that is newly introduced to the model. $K_{I,O_2,PB}$, $K_{I,E}$, and M_S
402 have not been reported in literature, yet are crucial for the proper function-
403 ing of the model based on their impact on the PPB abundance and COD
404 removal.

405 Model calibration combined with data of the three controlled experiments
406 reported by Alloul et al. (2021a), resulted in a value for $K_{S,O_2,PB}$, $K_{I,O_2,PB}$,
407 $K_{S,E}$, $K_{I,E}$ and M_S of $0.05 \text{ mgO}_2\text{L}^{-1}$, $5 \text{ mgO}_2\text{L}^{-1}$, 4 W m^{-2} , 135 W m^{-2} , and
408 0.28 respectively. Overall, the simulated and experimental outputs are in
409 good agreement and show a similar trend over the three operational strate-
410 gies, as depicted in Figure 1. In terms of relative error, the model has pre-
411 dicted the third scenario of the experiments more accurately than the other
412 two.

413 Two oxygen-PPB-related parameters were calibrated, namely the oxy-
414 gen half-saturation constant for aerobic chemoheterotrophic growth of PPB
415 ($K_{S,O_2,PB}$) and oxygen inhibitory constant for phototrophic growth of PPB
416 ($K_{I,O_2,PB}$). The oxygen half-saturation constant was calibrated to $0.05 \text{ mgO}_2\text{L}^{-1}$,
417 which is aligned with the oxygen half-saturation constant for AEB in the ac-
418 tivated sludge model (Henze et al., 2015). The second oxygen-PPB-related
419 parameter, i.e. $K_{I,O_2,PB}$, is responsible for the direct oxygen suppression of
420 the photoheterotrophic growth. A value of $5 \text{ mgO}_2\text{L}^{-1}$ is assigned to the pa-
421 rameter after calibration. Calibrating the oxygen inhibitory constant through
422 a dedicated experimental setup at different oxygen concentrations is challeng-
423 ing. PPB are able to grow both photo- and chemoheterotrophically. Increas-

424 ing the dissolved oxygen concentration even results in an enhancement of the
425 growth rate due to additional chemoheterotrophic conversion, e.g. 10% in-
426 crease in maximal specific growth rate subject to increase in oxygen transfer
427 from 72 to 336 mgO₂L⁻¹ (Alloul et al., 2021a). It should be highlighted that
428 next to dissolved oxygen concentration, the oxygen transfer rate is also a key
429 factor steering the microbial community in a raceway reactor. Together with
430 the oxygen uptake rate, it influences the actual dissolved Oxygen concentra-
431 tion in the system.

432 Two light-related parameters, i.e. $K_{S,E}$ and $K_{I,E}$ were also calibrated. The
433 calibrated value of $K_{I,E}$ is 4 W m⁻², in the range (i.e. 4.58±7.40 W m⁻²) re-
434 ported by Capson-Tojo et al. (2022). In comparison with other work and
435 their experiments such as Capson-Tojo et al. (2022); Katsuda et al. (2000),
436 it can be concluded that different wavelengths and inoculum result in other
437 type of pigment responsible for light capturing, which might also affect the ef-
438 fective the light half-saturation constant. The second calibrated light-related
439 parameter of the model inhibits the (an)aerobic chemoheterotrophic growth
440 of PPB. Along with $K_{I,O_2,PB}$, it enables the PPB community to allocate their
441 metabolic growth pathway between photo- and chemoheterotrophy.

442 The parallel metabolic growth factor (M_S) as the final parameter consid-
443 ered for calibration, allows PPB to account different metabolisms in parallel.
444 An M_S of zero would imply that the three metabolic growth modes of PPB,
445 namely photoheterotrophy, aerobic and aerobic chemoheterotrophy are com-
446 pletely independent and an M_S of one entails that PPB can deploy all three
447 metabolisms at once. The final calibrated value is assigned to 0.28. This
448 suggests that the PPB growth in a raceway reactor is probably not governed

449 by independent subpopulations, however individual PPB cells may switch
450 between metabolism. The experiments done by Alloul et al. (2021b) showed
451 that the PPB species *Rhodobacter capsulatus*, *Rb. sphaeroides*, *Rhodopseu-*
452 *domonas palustris* and *Rhodospirillum rubrum* are able to switch from pho-
453 toheterotrophy to aerobic chemoheterotrophy and from photoheterotrophy
454 to photoautotrophy, which supports the idea of integrating the metabolic
455 constant to the PBM.

456 *Perturbed scenario assessment:* The effect of process and environmental
457 perturbations, which are likely-to-occur in pilot- and full-scale raceway sys-
458 tems, was assessed with respect to the stability of the PPB community. Four
459 different perturbation scenarios, as described above, were simulated.

460 The wastewater composition can change throughout the day. The effect
461 of influent VFA variability (500–3000 mg COD L⁻¹) was, therefore, assessed
462 on the model performance. This scenario is depicted in Figure 5 (A) showing
463 that the PPB abundance is immediately affected when the incoming VFA
464 concentration drops from 3000 to 500 mg COD L⁻¹. When organic carbon is
465 limited in the reactor, dissolved oxygen can freely increase up to 3 mgO₂L⁻¹.
466 This oxygen increase eventually inhibits the phototrophic growth of PPB.
467 Lowering the HRT and, thus, increasing the volumetric loading rate can be
468 a contingency measure, yet the raceway reactor is typically designed for a
469 certain range in flow rate. Increasing the SRT is a better solution as it
470 increases the retention of PPB in the system, thereby, lowering the impact
471 of oxygen inhibition. The increase in oxygen still occurs, yet PPB is less
472 heavily affected. A faster contingency strategy would be decreasing paddle
473 wheel rotation or even stopping it completely. An oxygen sensor with paddle

474 wheel speed control can help to steer the oxygen transfer to the system to
475 cope with changes in loading rates during operation.

476 The second perturbation considered the effect of soluble organic mat-
477 ters (non-VFA matters) in the incoming wastewater ($0\text{--}3000\text{ mg COD L}^{-1}$).
478 For PPB systems, several articles recommended to preferment the wastew-
479 ater, thereby, separating acidogenic fermentation and PPB biomass produc-
480 tion (Alloul et al., 2021a, 2018; Cerruti et al., 2023). This would result
481 in lower competition with acidogenic fermentative microorganisms and pro-
482 vides more accessible organic carbon in the form of VFA for PPB to grow.
483 PPB are also able to ferment, yet their maximal specific anaerobic chemo-
484 heterotrophic growth rate is lower compared to non-PPB, i.e. 0.3 vs 0.6 d^{-1}
485 (Alloul et al., 2021a). For instance, PPB cannot compete with acidogenic
486 fermenters on sucrose-rich synthetic wastewater (Cerruti et al., 2023). The
487 perturbations reconfirmed these experimental observations as shown in Fig-
488 ure 5(B), in which a drop in relative PPB abundance from 30% to 11% when
489 the wastewater composition changes from 100% VFA to 100% non-VFA.

490 The third perturbation simulates variations in influent suspended solids.
491 These organics can cause higher turbidity of the water and, thereby, lower the
492 light availability for phototrophs and less PPB abundance as depicted in Fig-
493 ure 5 (C). Suspended solids concentrations as low as 250 mg COD L^{-1} drops
494 the PPB abundance from 26% to 18% . Suspended solids concentrations of
495 $1000\text{ mg COD L}^{-1}$ results in a complete collapse of the PPB community. In
496 this case, stopping the feed and operate the reactor in semi-continuous mode
497 until full recovery achieved again would be a solution. The results also show
498 that a good solid/liquid separation is crucial to prevent suspended material

499 from entering the raceway reactor.

500 Light intensity was the last studied perturbation. The results again show
501 a serious disruption on the PPB community, as shown in Figure 5 (D). As
502 expected, variations of light intensity have an important impact on the sta-
503 bility of the phototrophic community; when the light intensity decreases from
504 108 to 14 W m⁻² for 10 days, the final PPB abundance decreases from 27 %
505 to 7%.

506 *Model implications and further development:* The proposed model is the
507 first mechanistic model applicable for simulation of raceway-pond reactors
508 for cultivating PPB, considering the metabolic-mechanistic understanding of
509 PPB-based bacterial guilds involved in these systems. The calibrated model
510 is able to simulate potential perturbations in these types of reactors, subject
511 to light variations as well as aeration promotion. Similar to activated sludge
512 systems designed for phosphorus removal, a pre-fermentation tank can help
513 solubilize the organic matter as VFAs to better select for PPB (Cerruti et al.,
514 2023) in the raceway system, which was taken into account for modeling.

515 To reduce the multiscale complexity of the PBM, simplifications on metab-
516 olisms that PPB can adopt in nature were made. For instance, photolithoau-
517 totrophic growth by PPB on carbon dioxide as a carbon source and dihydro-
518 gen or iron II as electron donors, and N₂-fixation by PPB were not included.
519 These latter metabolisms are less likely to occur in the raceway reactor. How-
520 ever, depending on local conditions to be studied, the PBM structure can
521 be adapted. Species or strain specific metabolic traits of PPB such as deni-
522 trification, and autotrophic uptake of hydrogen are also not adopted in the
523 model for the sake of simplicity and the type of raceway reactor.

524 For further modeling improvement, other PPB metabolisms and micro-
525 bial community can be included, considering losing simplicity for simulation
526 application to increasing accuracy for detailed biological analysis. The in-
527 tegration of temperature dependency and dynamic pH of the biological and
528 other physical processes can also be other added depending on an operational
529 condition under consideration, since the temperature and pH are considered
530 to be fixed in the PBM.

531 Since PBM is a new mechanistic model for PPB community in terms of
532 metabolic-mechanistic understanding, the transfer of biotechnology from a
533 proof-of-concept to practical application requires a proof-of-feasibility. Cali-
534 brating the model under various conditions and configurations would enable
535 expanding its applicability and accuracy. Additionally, conducting estima-
536 tions of kinetic parameters using different substrates and light ranges is also
537 crucial, in which more experiments should be carried out to evaluate these
538 options.

539 **4. Conclusions**

540 In this paper, a new mechanistic model to describe the mechanisms of
541 microbial selection, competition and conversions in an open raceway reactor
542 is proposed. The model integrates three different metabolisms of PPB, and
543 competing aerobic and anaerobic organisms that can prevail in a raceway
544 reactor. Integration of parallel metabolic growth is modelled. The model
545 was shown to be able to accurately predict changes in the PPB abundance
546 and COD removal rates with the relative errors 19.5 % and 12 %, respectively.
547 The outputs of the simulated perturbation scenarios were shown to capture

548 both theoretical understanding and experimental observations of PPB-based
549 processes.

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634 Figure 1: Effects of the perturbation scenarios on relative PPB abundance
635 based on variations on (A) influent VFA (250, 500, and 3000 mg COD L⁻¹),
636 (B) influent soluble organic (non-VFA) (0, 100, and 3000 mg COD L⁻¹), (C)
637 influent suspended solid (0, 250, and 1000 mg COD L⁻¹), and (D) light (14,
638 54, and 108 W m⁻²). The perturbation was applied on day 25.

Table 1: State variables included in the PBM categorized in a particulate (X) and soluble (S) fraction. Microbial biomass in forms of purple phototrophic bacteria (indexed by PB), aerobic bacteria (AEB) and anaerobic bacteria (ANB). PPB can be grown photoheterotrophically (ph), aerobic chemoheterotrophically (aec), and anaerobic chemoheterotrophically (anc).

Symbol	Description	Unit
Microbial biomass		
$X_{PB,ph}$	Photoheterotropic grown PPB	mg COD L ⁻¹
$X_{PB,aec}$	Aerobic chemoheterotropic grown PPB	mg COD L ⁻¹
$X_{PB,anc}$	Anaerobic chemoheterotropic grown PPB	mg COD L ⁻¹
X_{AEB}	Aerobic bacteria	mg COD L ⁻¹
X_{ANB}	Anaerobic bacteria	mg COD L ⁻¹
Substrates and products		
X_S	Slowly biodegradable organic matter	mg COD L ⁻¹
X_I	Inert particulate organic matter	mg COD L ⁻¹
S_S	Readily biodegradable organic matter	mg COD L ⁻¹
S_{VFA}	Volatile fatty acids	mg COD L ⁻¹
S_I	Inert soluble organic matter	mg COD L ⁻¹
S_{H_2}	Soluble hydrogen	mg COD L ⁻¹
S_{IC}	Total inorganic carbon	mmolHCO ₃ ⁻ L ⁻¹
S_{IN}	Total inorganic nitrogen	mgNL ⁻¹
S_{IP}	Total inorganic phosphorus	mgPL ⁻¹
S_{O_2}	Dissolved oxygen	mgO ₂ L ⁻¹

Table 2: Peterson matrix of the PBM. The model contains 12 biological, 4 physical processes with 15 state variables. Biological processes are grouped according to the type of microorganism involved, namely purple bacteria, aerobic bacteria (AEB), and anaerobic bacteria (ANB). Process rates are presented in Table 3, stoichiometric coefficients and parameter values can be found in the supplementary materials.

Process (↓)	State Variable (→)	S_{O_2}	S_S	S_{VFA}	S_{IC}	S_{H_2}	S_{N_2}	S_I	$X_{PB,ph}$	$X_{PB,acc}$	X_{AEB}	X_{ANB}	X_S	Process rate (↓)
Purple bacteria (X_{PB})														
Photoheterotrophic growth on S_S		0	$-1/Y_{PB,ph}$	0	$f_{IC,ph,SS}$	0	$-X_{N,PB}$	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Photoheterotrophic growth on S_{VFA}		0	$-1/Y_{PB,ph}$	0	$f_{IC,ph,VFA}$	0	$-X_{N,PB}$	0	1	0	0	0	0	2
Aerobic chemoheterotrophic growth S_S		$-(1 - Y_{PB,acc})/Y_{PB,acc}$	$-1/Y_{PB,acc}$	0	$f_{IC,acc,SS}$	0	$-X_{N,PB}$	0	0	1	0	0	0	3
Aerobic chemoheterotrophic growth S_{VFA}		$-(1 - Y_{PB,acc})/Y_{PB,acc}$	$-1/Y_{PB,acc}$	0	$f_{IC,acc,VFA}$	0	$-X_{N,PB}$	0	0	1	0	0	0	4
Anaerobic chemoheterotrophic growth S_S		0	$-1/Y_{PB,acc}$	0	$f_{IC,acc,SS}$	0	$-X_{N,PB}$	0	0	0	1	0	0	5
Decay of $X_{PB} = X_{PB,ph} + X_{PB,acc}$		0	0	0	$f_{IC,dec}$	0	$f_{IN,dec}$	0	-1	-1	0	0	1	6
Aerobic bacteria (X_{AEB})														
Aerobic chemoheterotrophic growth on S_S		$-(1 - Y_{AEB})/Y_{AEB}$	$-1/Y_{AEB}$	0	$f_{IC,AEB,SS}$	0	$Y_{N,AEB}$	0	0	0	0	1	0	7
Aerobic chemoheterotrophic growth on S_{VFA}		$-(1 - Y_{AEB})/Y_{AEB}$	$-1/Y_{AEB}$	0	$f_{IC,AEB,VFA}$	0	$Y_{N,AEB}$	0	0	0	1	0	0	8
Decay of X_{AEB}		0	0	0	$f_{IC,dec}$	0	$f_{IN,dec}$	0	0	0	-1	0	1	9
Anaerobic bacteria (X_{ANB})														
Anaerobic chemoheterotrophic growth on S_S		0	$-1/Y_{ANB}$	$f_{VFA,ANB,SS}/Y_{ANB}$	$f_{IC,ANB,SS}$	$f_{VFA,ANB,H_2}/Y_{ANB}$	$-X_{N,ANB}$	0	0	0	0	1	0	10
Decay of X_{ANB}		0	0	0	$f_{IC,dec}$	0	$f_{IN,dec}$	0	0	0	0	-1	1	11
Hydrolysis														
		0	$f_{S,S}$	$f_{VFA,S}$	$f_{IC,S}$	$f_{H_2,S}$	$f_{IN,S}$	$f_{I,S}$	0	0	0	0	-1	12
Physical processes														
Oxygen dissolution		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13
Carbon dioxide stripping/dissolution		0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14
Nitrogen stripping		0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15
Nitrogen stripping		0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	16

Table 3: Biological and physical process rates in the PBM according to Table 2

$\rho(\cdot)$	Description	Rate equation
Purple bacteria (X_{PB})		
1	Photoheterotrophic growth on soluble organics such as carbohydrates and alcohols (excluding VFA).	$\mu_{m,SS,P,ph} \frac{S_E}{S_E + K_{T,E}} \frac{S_{O_2} + K_{LO_2,PH}}{S_{O_2} + K_{LO_2,PH}} \frac{S_{IN}}{S_{IN} + K_{S,IN}} \frac{S_{IP}}{S_{IP} + K_{S,IP}} \frac{S_S}{S_S + S_{VFA}} \frac{S_S}{S_S + K_{S,PH}} f_{ph}(X_{PB}, M_S)$
2	Photoheterotrophic growth on VFA. The main products are biomass and carbon dioxide.	$\mu_{m,VFA,PH,ph} \frac{S_E + K_{T,E}}{S_E} \frac{S_{O_2} + K_{LO_2,PH}}{S_{O_2} + K_{LO_2,PH}} \frac{S_{IN}}{S_{IN} + K_{S,IN}} \frac{S_{IP}}{S_{IP} + K_{S,IP}} \frac{S_S + S_{VFA}}{S_S + S_{VFA}} \frac{S_{VFA}}{S_{VFA} + K_{S,VFA,ph}} f_{ph}(X_{PB}, M_S)$
3	Aerobic chemoheterotrophic growth on soluble organics with oxygen as terminal electron acceptor.	$\mu_{m,SS,P,B,aer} \frac{S_E + K_{T,E}}{S_E} \frac{S_{O_2} + K_{LO_2,PH}}{S_{O_2} + K_{LO_2,PH}} \frac{S_{IN}}{S_{IN} + K_{S,IN}} \frac{S_{IP}}{S_{IP} + K_{S,IP}} \frac{S_S + S_{VFA}}{S_S + S_{VFA}} \frac{S_S + K_{S,aer}}{S_S + K_{S,aer}} f_{aer}(X_{PB}, M_S)$
4	Aerobic chemoheterotrophic growth on VFA.	$\mu_{m,VFA,P,B,aer} \frac{K_{S,E}}{S_E} \frac{S_{O_2} + K_{LO_2,PH}}{S_{O_2} + K_{LO_2,PH}} \frac{S_{IN}}{S_{IN} + K_{S,IN}} \frac{S_{IP}}{S_{IP} + K_{S,IP}} \frac{S_S + S_{VFA}}{S_S + S_{VFA}} \frac{S_{VFA}}{S_{VFA} + K_{S,VFA,aer}} f_{aer}(X_{PB}, M_S)$
5	Anaerobic chemoheterotrophic growth and acidogenic fermentation reactions on soluble organics. The main products are biomass, hydrogen, carbon dioxide and VFA.	$\mu_{m,SS,P,B,anaer} \frac{K_{S,E}}{S_E} \frac{K_{LO_2,anaer}}{S_{O_2} + K_{LO_2,anaer}} \frac{S_{IN}}{S_{IN} + K_{S,IN}} \frac{S_{IP}}{S_{IP} + K_{S,IP}} \frac{S_S}{S_S + K_{S,anaer}} f_{anaer}(X_{PB}, M_S)$
6	Decay of PPB biomass into biodegradable (X_S) and inert (X_I) organic matter and release of ammonium, phosphate, and bicarbonate.	$b_{m,PPB,dec}(X_{PB,ph} + X_{PB,aer} + X_{PB,anaer})$
Aerobic bacteria (X_{AEB})		
7	Aerobic chemoheterotrophic growth on soluble organics with oxygen as terminal electron acceptor.	$\mu_{m,SS,AEB} \frac{K_{S,aer}}{S_{O_2} + K_{S02,aer,AEB}} \frac{S_{IN}}{S_{IN} + K_{S,IN}} \frac{S_{IP}}{S_{IP} + K_{S,IP}} \frac{S_S}{S_S + S_{VFA}} \frac{S_S}{S_S + K_{S,AEB}} \frac{X_{AEB}}{X_{AEB}}$
8	Aerobic chemoheterotrophic growth on VFA.	$\mu_{m,VFA,AEB} \frac{K_{S02,aer}}{S_{O_2} + K_{S02,aer,AEB}} \frac{S_{IN}}{S_{IN} + K_{S,IN}} \frac{S_{IP}}{S_{IP} + K_{S,IP}} \frac{S_S + S_{VFA}}{S_S + S_{VFA}} \frac{S_{VFA}}{S_{VFA} + K_{S,VFA,AEB}} \frac{X_{AEB}}{X_{AEB}}$
9	Decay of AEB biomass into biodegradable (X_S) and inert (X_I) organic matter and release of ammonium, phosphate, and bicarbonate.	$b_{m,AEB,dec} X_{AEB}$
Anaerobic bacteria (X_{ANB})		
10	Anaerobic chemoheterotrophic growth and acidogenic fermentation reactions on soluble organics. The main products are biomass, hydrogen, carbon dioxide and VFA.	$\mu_{m,VFA,ANB} \frac{K_{S02,ANB}}{S_{O_2} + K_{S02,ANB}} \frac{S_{IN}}{S_{IN} + K_{S,IN}} \frac{S_{IP}}{S_{IP} + K_{S,IP}} \frac{S_S}{S_S + K_{S,ANB}} \frac{S_S}{S_S + K_{S,ANB}} X_{ANB}$
11	Decay of ANB biomass into biodegradable (X_S) and inert (X_I) organic matter and release of ammonium, phosphate, and bicarbonate.	$b_{m,ANB,dec} X_{ANB}$
Hydrolysis		
12	Hydrolysis of biodegradable particulates (X_S) into soluble (S_C and S_{VFA}) and inert organic carbon (X_I), ammonium, hydrogen and bicarbonate.	$\mu_{hydro} X_S$
Physical processes		
13	Stripping/dissolution of oxygen in raceway reactor.	$K(a_{O_2}(O_2^{sat} - S_{O_2}))$
14	Stripping/dissolution of carbon dioxide in raceway reactor.	$K(a_{CO_2}(CO_2^{sat} - S_{O_2}))$
15	Stripping of hydrogen in raceway reactor.	$K(a_{H_2}(H_2^{sat} - S_{H_2}))$
16	Stripping of ammonium in raceway reactor.	$K(a_{NH_3}(NH_3^{sat} - S_{NH_3}))$

Table 4: Sensitivity analysis of the most impactful kinetic parameters of the PBM. Sensitivity analysis is computed by changing the default value of each parameter one by one, ten times higher and lower, while keeping the other parameters constant. The mean for the PPB abundance, chemical oxygen demand (COD) removal rate (mg COD removed $L^{-1} d^{-1}$), biomass productivity (mg COD biomass d^{-1}) and the biomass yield (mg COD biomass mgCODremoved) of the last five days for each iteration is calculated and divided by the output results of the baseline (default values) to obtain the relative error. The impact represents the slopes between the relative error (y -axis) and the relative change in parameter's value (x -axis).

Parameter (unit)	Symbol	Default	Impact on			
			PPB abundance	COD removal	Biomass productivity	Biomass yield
Parallel metabolic growth (-)	M_S	0.300	13.98	0.33	1.72	-0.74
Maximal specific aerobic chemotrophic growth rate of PPB on soluble organics (d^{-1})	$\mu_{m,SS,AEB}$	0.076	-10.97	-10.97	-2.24	0.04
Maximal specific aerobic chemotrophic growth rate of PPB on volatile fatty acids (d^{-1})	$\mu_{m,VFA,AEB}$	0.053	10.94	-10.94	-0.60	0.07
Specific decay rate of PPB (d^{-1})	$b_{m,FB,dec}$	0.011	-10.11	-10.11	-2.29	0.54
Oxygen half-saturation constant for chemotrophic growth of PPB (mgO ₂ L ⁻¹)	$K_{S,O_2,FB}$	0.050	-9.92	-9.92	0.53	-0.08
Maximal specific phototrophic growth rate of PPB on volatile fatty acids (d^{-1})	$\mu_{m,VFA,FB,ph}$	0.078	9.90	9.90	2.09	-0.93
Oxygen half-saturation constant for AEB (mgO ₂ L ⁻¹)	$K_{S,O_2,AEB}$	0.050	-9.26	-9.26	-0.50	-0.06
Specific decay rate of AEB (mgO ₂ L ⁻¹)	$b_{m,AEB,dec}$	0.016	8.99	8.99	0.49	-0.06
Light half-saturation constant of PPB (W m ²)	$K_{S,E}$	4.500	-7.44	-7.44	0.39	2.29
Maximal specific aerobic chemotrophic growth rate of PPB on soluble organics (d^{-1})	$\mu_{m,SS,FB,acc}$	0.050	2.87	2.87	-0.16	-0.03
Maximal specific anaerobic chemotrophic growth rate of PPB on soluble organics (d^{-1})	$\mu_{m,SS,FB,anc}$	0.012	2.36	0.14	-0.13	0.07
Light inhibitory constant for chemotrophic growth of PPB (W m ²)	$K_{I,E}$	200.000	1.40	1.40	-0.09	-0.02
Maximal specific phototrophic growth rate of PPB on soluble organics (d^{-1})	$\mu_{m,SS,FB,ph}$	0.053	1.31	1.31	-0.07	0.04
Oxygen inhibitory constant for phototrophic growth of PPB (mgO ₂ L ⁻¹)	$K_{I,O_2,FB}$	5.000	1.20	0.00	-0.08	-0.02

Table 5: Calibration results including calibrated model outputs for relative purple phototrophic bacteria abundance, chemical oxygen demand (COD) removal rate, biomass productivity, and biomass yield and associated experimental data for three defined operational scenarios. Mean relative errors for the scenarios as well as mean relative errors for the selected outputs are also provided.

Scenario	Experiment and simulation conditions		Purple bacteria (Relative abundance %)		COD removal rate (mgCODL ⁻¹)		Biomass productivity (mgCODL ⁻¹)		Biomass yield (mg COD _{biomass} mg ⁻¹ COD _{removed})		Relative error (↓)
	Illumination (light/dark)	Stirring (on/off)	Surface-to-volume (m ² m ⁻³)	Experiment	Model	Experiment	Model	Experiment	Model	Experiment	
1	12h/12h	24h on	5	14	721.83	702.66	0.45	0.64	326	459	21.83
2	12h/12h	12h/12h	5	27	462.50	593.52	0.65	0.62	302	390	26.04
3	12h/12h	24h on	10	78	785.17	822.31	0.58	0.53	452	577	14.08
	Relative error (→)			19.50	11.90		18.57		32.62		-